

Max is a PhD-candidate working on an individual project. Over the years he has conducted several small research projects. In the end he decides two of these projects will not be a part of his PhD-dissertation, because they do not add any value to the main arguments. However, he believes the data sets and results are still interesting, and he feels that not using the research projects is a waste of the time and energy he invested in them. Max discusses his dilemma with one of his supervisors, a renowned scholar. She advises him to keep the research data for himself. She also suggests they could try to write an article together based on the research projects, after Max has obtained his PhD degree. This would mean he will not provide open access to the two datasets and its results after his PhD defense, instead keeping them private until he has time to write one or two articles based on the research projects.

- 1) Is Max obliged to publish the unused datasets and results in open access after his PhD defense?
- 2) Is there another solution that ensures 'open' access to the research data of Max, as well as keeping open the opportunity to write an article together with his supervisor?